

QUIZ**LAST NAME:** Klein**FIRST NAME:** Angela**PROGRAM CODE:** DIRD**COURSE CODE :** ACA 401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied XUS UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author Xdid did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- When citing interviews using (author-date) style, the following is true:**
 - Do not cite, in parenthesis, within the text.
 - Do not list citation within the bibliography unless used frequently within the text.
 - For both published and unpublished interview citations, treat the interviewee as the author.
 - For in-text citations, use (the name of the person interviewed – date).¹**
- To make the most of feedback, a writer must decide if she has been given *advice* or *data*. Good advice looks like:**

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Ninth edition (Chicago; London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 264-5.

- Data or misunderstanding that gives you unclear advice, but that you can investigate further to understand what created the misunderstanding.
 - Corrections in spelling, punctuation or grammar.
 - Personal judgments of your writing.
 - All of the above.**²
3. **US convention on punctuation should be included within quotation marks or inverted commas. Quotation marks are used for direct speech and inverted commas are used to set words or statements apart. Which of the following sentences is correct?**
- A common greeting during Muslim holidays is “Kul ‘am wa enta bi-Khair”, which means ‘May every year find you in good health’.
 - A common greeting during Muslim holidays is ‘Kul ‘am wa enta bi-Khair’, which means ‘May every year find you in good health’.
 - A common greeting during Muslim holidays is ‘Kul ‘am wa enta bi-Khair,’ which means ‘May every year find you in good health.’**³
 - A common greeting during Muslim holidays is ‘Kul ‘am wa enta bi-Khair’, which means ‘May every year find you in good health.’
4. **An example of plagiarism is:**
- Using a direct quotation and acknowledging, within the text, the author and title of the text.

² Turabian, 124-5.

³ Turabian, 315.

- Not acknowledging that someone has edited your work.
 - Copy and paste a quote from the internet.**⁴
 - When the information is common knowledge and can be found in more than one source.
5. **When testing the relevance of a reason to a claim; a warrant must bridge them. For a reader to accept the claim, the following must be true:**
- The specific reason is sometimes true.
 - The warrant must be true.**⁵
 - Conditions prevent the warrant from being true.
 - The reader could come up with an argument against the general condition or the general consequence of the warrant.
6. **The chapter of the dissertation that includes: the overview of the methodology, analysis and synthesis of data, issues of trustworthiness, and limitations, is chapter:**
- 4 – Presentation of findings.
 - 2 – Literature review.
 - 3 - Research Methodology.**⁶
 - 5 - Analysis and interpretation of findings.

⁴ EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. Washington DC: Euclid. UniversityPress. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed January, 2020), 8-13.

⁵ Turabian, 61.

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing the Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Sage Publications, Inc., 2008), 31.

7. **The *abstract* is a summary of the work of your dissertation. It should not:**

- Include the research question addressed.
- Be restricted to 500 words.**⁷
- Include your research methodology.
- List key findings, conclusions, and recommendations.

8. **The following is an aspect of Social Constructivism, Interpretivism, or Naturalistic inquiry:**

- Reality is socially, historically and culturally constructed.**⁸
- Reality can be reduced to its component parts.
- Knowledge arises out of actions, situations or consequences.
- Includes feminist perspectives.

9. **Complete the following sentence with the correct word. In qualitative research, _____ findings are those that are meaningful, important, or useful.**

- Consistent
- Relevant
- Convincing
- Significant**⁹

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 168.

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 8-9.

⁹ Turabian, 54.

10. **Zotero can be used to:**

- Change format to different styles while already in process or already completed.** ¹⁰
- Format citations so that you do not have to worry about them.
- Predict citations based on quotations used in-text.
- Check and correct the spelling, grammar, punctuation in your writing.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Sage Publications, Inc., 2008.

EUCLID. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed January 2020), 2015.

Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Ninth edition Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Laurent Cleenewerk, “Zotero Training 1 and 2”, August 8, 2017, video, 12:59, <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-2/>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰ Laurent Cleenewerk, “Zotero Training 1 and 2”, August 8, 2017, video, 12:59, <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-2/>.